

PACIFICUS

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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE CALLING I ONCE REFUSED”

I never dreamed that I would teach,
Such a path felt far from reach.
I sought the badge, I tried, I failed,
Yet God’s design still prevailed.

Through hardship, study, work, and strife,
I found new purpose in this life.
Each student’s smile, each lesson true,
Revealed the calling I once withdrew.

Now I see with grateful eyes,
God’s plans are perfect, strong, and wise.
What I resisted, He gave to me—
A noble calling, my destiny.